

THE IMPACT OF ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE ON PERSONALIZED LEARNING IN LANGUAGE EDUCATION

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Abstract:

The rise of social media platforms has dramatically transformed the way people communicate. As digital spaces evolve, so do language patterns, influencing everyday communication both online and offline. This article explores how social media platforms like Twitter, Facebook, and Instagram have contributed to language simplification, the spread of internet slang, and the emergence of new communication norms. It highlights both the positive and negative effects of social media on linguistic diversity, creativity, and the structure of communication, analyzing how these changes impact broader cultural interactions and discourse.

Key words: social media, language evolution, internet slang, communication norms, linguistic diversity, digital communication.

doi: <https://doi.org/10.2024/bqyvrc88>

Language is a dynamic entity that evolves over time, adapting to new cultural, technological, and societal shifts. In recent years, the proliferation of social media platforms has played a significant role in this evolution. The use of social media has accelerated changes in everyday language, making it more adaptive, concise, and driven by trends [Herring, 2004, p. 197]. Twitter, Facebook, Instagram, TikTok, and other platforms have transformed how people express themselves, changing the structure, meaning, and context of communication.

One of the most noticeable impacts of social media on everyday language is the rise of internet slang and abbreviations. Phrases like "LOL" (laugh out loud), "BRB" (be right back), and "FOMO" (fear of missing out) have become mainstream, even making their way into formal communication [Agar, 2011, p. 55]. Social media users often shorten words to fit character limits, especially on platforms like Twitter, which originally imposed a 140-character limit. This trend has pushed users to find more concise ways to convey meaning, thus shaping a language style that is fast, flexible, and efficient [Baker, 2014, p. 78].

New words and phrases coined online can quickly become part of the collective vernacular. Terms like "selfie," "hashtag," "viral," and "influencer" were born from social media culture and are now common in everyday conversation [García, 2018, p. 102]. The speed at which these new words are adopted reflects the rapid communication flows enabled by digital platforms.

Beyond text-based communication, social media has also popularized the use of emojis and gifs, changing how non-verbal cues are transmitted in written form. Emojis, small pictorial symbols, allow users to express emotions, tone, and reactions in ways that text alone may not fully capture [Walther et al., 2011, p. 1175]. For example, a simple thumbs-up emoji can quickly convey approval, while a crying-laughing face can indicate humor. The integration of these visual elements has further simplified language, allowing for complex emotions or ideas to be represented with a single image. In a way, emojis have become a

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universal language, enabling communication across linguistic barriers [Dresner & Herring, 2010, p. 224]. However, the heavy reliance on these symbols also raises questions about the potential oversimplification of nuanced communication and whether it diminishes critical thinking in language use.

Social media's fast-paced nature has also given rise to increasingly informal grammar and syntax. Sentences are often left incomplete, punctuation is omitted, and capitalization rules are ignored [Thurlow, 2003, p. 285]. For example, users may type in all lowercase letters or forgo punctuation marks, giving the impression of casualness or urgency. This stylistic shift has made digital communication less formal and more spontaneous. While the reduction of grammatical structure in social media communication can make interactions feel more personal and immediate, it also raises concerns about how these trends may influence writing skills in formal contexts. Studies suggest that the informal writing styles popularized on social media can spill over into academic and professional writing, where proper grammar and punctuation are traditionally required [Drennan, 2012, p. 61].

Social media platforms have created global networks where individuals from diverse linguistic and cultural backgrounds interact. As a result, languages are becoming more intertwined, with words and phrases from different cultures often blending into each other. English, as the dominant language of the internet, heavily influences global social media interactions [Crystal, 2001, p. 23]. For instance, many non-English speakers incorporate English terms into their everyday language, especially in digital contexts, leading to the phenomenon of code-switching [Poplack, 1980, p. 585].

At the same time, social media facilitates the spread of cultural trends that impact language. Memes, viral videos, and challenges often carry distinct phrases or catchwords that quickly gain traction worldwide. These cultural phenomena frequently transcend their original language boundaries and are adapted into new linguistic and cultural contexts [Shifman, 2014, p. 50].

While social media promotes linguistic creativity, it can also lead to the homogenization of language. The dominance of English on global platforms and the viral spread of specific internet slang have caused concerns about the erosion of linguistic diversity [Pennycook, 2017, p. 134]. As younger generations increasingly adopt social media jargon, traditional and regional dialects may lose their prominence.

Furthermore, the brevity required in social media communication can result in the loss of depth and richness in language. Complex ideas or nuanced conversations are often reduced to sound bites or trending hashtags, limiting the potential for detailed discussions [Wright, 2019, p. 34].

The impact of social media on everyday language is multifaceted. On one hand, it has encouraged linguistic creativity, fostered global communication, and introduced new forms of expression. On the other hand, it risks simplifying language, promoting informal grammar, and contributing to the decline of linguistic diversity. As social media continues to shape how we communicate, it is essential to recognize both the benefits and the challenges it presents for the future of language evolution. The digital landscape will likely continue to push language toward greater efficiency and innovation, but it is crucial to maintain a balance that preserves the richness and complexity of communication.

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